

Awareness of Family Physicians towards Antihistamines in Allergic Disorders and Pruritis; a Study Conducted On 130 Family Physicians in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Background: Antihistamines are commonly prescribed in allergic disorders and pruritis. Antihistamines have two generations, first generation having more side effects, while second generation is safe. In our community dermatologists are few in number so mostly family physicians deal with such patients having skin allergies or pruritis and they initially prescribe them antihistamines, so it is necessary to know their awareness about antihistamines use.

Study design & duration: This is a descriptive study completed in duration of six months from January to June 2019.

Setting: Study was conducted on physicians and dermatologists belonging to Hyderabad and Bahawalpur cities.

Patients and methods: One hundred family physician doctors were included in this study after taking informed consent from them. A validated-questionnaire was designed containing 10 questions about awareness and prescribing schedule of antihistamines, which was filled up and its data was analyzed using statistical software SPSS-20. Chi-square test was applied. Results were calculated in the form of percentages and means, were expressed via tables and graphs. P-value less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results: Out of total 130 physicians, 35% prescribed first generation of antihistamines while 65% prescribed second generation. Only 20% doctors were aware about ARIA and GA2LEN guidelines about giving priority to second generation antihistamines over older first generation, while 80% were not aware about it. About 65% physicians prescribed various antihistamines to their patients depending on age, pregnancy status and occupation, while 35% did not consider these factors. Only 62% doctors counseled their patients about taking rest, avoid taking alcohol and not to drive while they are taking antihistamine treatment. 10% physicians used to updose 3-4 times same antihistamine in their patients while 90% did not do that.

Conclusion: Although most of the family physicians prescribe second generation antihistamine while many of them were not aware properly to their dosing guidelines.

Key words: Allergic disorders, pruritis, urticaria, antihistamines, guidelines

INTRODUCTION

Antihistamines are commonly used by physicians and dermatologists in general practice for allergic reaction like pruritis, urticaria, vasculitis etc.¹ It is also used in severe conditions like angioedema, anaphylaxis, allergic rhinitis, asthma and conjunctivitis. Early diagnosis of allergic conditions and immediate treatment with anti-allergic medication is necessary otherwise anaphylaxis may be life threatening. There are various types of anti-histamines according to their action on different receptor sites like H1, H2 and H3.² For pruritis and common allergic reactions H1 are given. H1 antihistamines have been derived from anticholinergic class of drugs which have more sedative effects than second generation. These are very much effective against allergic reactions. Second generation antihistamines are advanced than first generation having less CNS sedative effects.³ Antihistamines can be given as anticonvulsants, tranquilizer, hypnotic and decongestant. Antihistamines are divided into first and second generations depending on their effect on CNS. First generation included diphenhydramine, chlorpheniramine and hydroxazin, while second generation includes cetirazine, loratadine, fexofenadine, desloratadin and levocitrazin.⁴ Second generation is used commonly these days due to low sedative effect as compared to first generation.⁵

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This is a cross sectional study conducted on physicians belonging to Hyderabad and Bahawalpur city. This study was started in January 2019 and completed after duration of six months in June 2019. Patients were included in the study according to predesigned inclusion and exclusion criteria. One hundred family physician doctors were included in this study after taking informed consent from them. A validated-questionnaire was

designed containing 10 questions about awareness and prescribing schedule of antihistamines, which was filled up and its data was analyzed using statistical software SPSS-20. Chi-square test was applied. Results were calculated in the form of percentages and means, were expressed via tables and graphs. P-value less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant. Confidence Interval in this study was 95% and margin of error was 5%. Ethical issues were considered during study period and privacy of data was maintained. There was no conflict of interest in authors.

Results:

Out of total 130 physicians, 47(35%) prescribed first generation of antihistamines while 84(65%) prescribed second generation. Only 26(20%) doctors were aware about ARIA and GA2LEN

guidelines about giving priority to second generation antihistamines over older first generation, while 104(80%) were not aware about it. About 84(65%) physicians prescribed various antihistamines to their patients depending on age, pregnancy status and occupation, while 45(35%) did not consider these factors. Only 80(62%) doctors counseled their patients about taking rest, avoid taking alcohol and not to drive while they are taking antihistamine treatment. 13(10%) physicians used to increase dose 3-4 times same antihistamine in their patients while 117(90%) did not do that. 27 doctors told that their patients asked them to advise first generation antihistamines as they get better result from it. 26 doctors were advising according to their patients choice and remaining 104 doctors were not guided by their patients demand.

Frequency of physicians prescribing first and second generation antihistamines (n=130).

DISCUSSION

H1 antihistamines have been derived from anticholinergic class of drugs which have more sedative effects than second generation.⁶ These are very much effective against allergic reactions. Second generation antihistamines are advanced than first generation having less CNS sedative effects.⁷ Antihistamines can be given as anticonvulsants, tranquilizer, hypnotic and decongestant.⁸ They have role in epilepsy as well. Additional side effects of first generation are somnolence, fatigue, headache, mydriasis, dryness of mouth and eyes, constipation, urinary retention, postural hypotension due to peripheral vasodilation. Antihistamines are commonly used by physicians and dermatologists in general practice for allergic reaction like pruritis, urticaria,

vasculitis etc.⁹⁻¹¹ It is also used in severe conditions like angioedema, anaphylaxis, allergic rhinitis, asthma and conjunctivitis. Early diagnosis of allergic conditions and immediate treatment with anti-allergic medication is necessary otherwise anaphylaxis may be life threatening. There are various types of anti-histamines according to their action on different receptor sites like H1, H2 and H3.¹²⁻¹⁴ Out of total 130 physicians, 47(35%) prescribed first generation of antihistamines while 84(65%) prescribed second generation. Only 26(20%) doctors were aware about ARIA and GA2LEN guidelines about giving priority to second generation antihistamines over older first generation, while 104(80%) were not aware about it. About 84(65%) physicians prescribed various antihistamines to their patients depending on age, pregnancy status and occupation, while 45(35%)

did not consider these factors. Only 80(62%) doctors counseled their patients about taking rest, avoid taking alcohol and not to drive while they are taking antihistamine treatment. For pruritis and common allergic reactions H1 are given. Antihistamines are divided into first and second generations depending on their effect on CNS.^{15,16} This is a cross sectional study conducted on physicians belonging to Hyderabad and Bahawalpur city. This study was started in January 2019 and completed after duration of six months in June 2019. Patients were included in the study according to predesigned inclusion and exclusion criteria. One hundred family physician doctors were included in this study after taking informed consent from them. A validated-questionnaire was

designed containing 10 questions about awareness and prescribing schedule of antihistamines, which was filled up and its data was analyzed using statistical software SPSS-20. Chi-square test was applied.

CONCLUSION

Antihistamines are commonly used by general practitioners in our community. There are many indications for prescribing it but they are usually prescribed for allergic reactions and urticarial and pruritis. Second generation antihistamines are prescribed by most of the doctors due to its less side effects and decreased sedation as compared to first generation antihistamines having more effect on CNS.

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